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Leveraging Management Information Systems For Enhanced Organisational Performance: Evidence From Selected Tertiary Institutions In Sokoto State

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ABSTRACT

Over the years, billions of naira have been disbursed to public tertiary institutions in Nigeria for infrastructure, ICT development, staff training and research support. Despite these investments, optimal performance through Management Information System (MIS) has not been achieved. The effect of MIS on organisational performance was examined in Sokoto State University, Umaru Ali Shinkafi Polytechnic and Shehu Shagari College of Education renamed as University of Education. Data were collected quantitatively using structured questionnaire from 123 non-academic staff in MIS/ICT related departments, with respondents selected through proportionate stratified sampling technique to ensure representation across institutions. Multiple regression analysis was employed to assess the effect of MIS on organizational performance. The findings indicated that proper MIS application significantly improved efficiency, reporting and administrative coordination. However, MIS utilization was found to have a positive but statistically insignificant effect, reflecting the reality that revealed underutilisation, weak integration and continue reliance on manual processes. Conversely, staff competence in operating MIS was shown to significantly enhance organizational performance, demonstrating the important of skilled personnel. Based on these findings, full integration of MIS into daily operations and continuous capacity-building programme were recommended to strengthen staff skills allowing MIS to contribute manfully to long-term institutional performance

Keywords: Management Information Systems, Organizational Performance, Staff Competence, Tertiary Institutions, Sokoto State.

INTRODUCTION

Organizational performance is a key indicator of how effectively institutions use available resources to achieve their goals and deliver value to stakeholders. In tertiary institutions, performance is reflected in the quality of academic administration, student services, staff management, financial control, research coordination, and decision-making processes. As institutions become more complex, achieving high performance increasingly depends on the ability to generate, process, and use reliable information in a timely manner. This makes information management a critical factor in institutional success.

In response to rising demands for efficiency and accountability, tertiary institutions around the world have increasingly adopted Management Information Systems (MIS) as a strategic tool for improving performance. MIS refers to integrated systems that collect, store, and process data to support managerial planning, coordination, control, and decision-making (Laudon & Laudon, 2022). Evidence from developed countries shows that effective use of MIS improves operational efficiency, reduces

administrative delays, enhances transparency, and supports data-driven management in higher education institutions (OECD, 2020). However, even globally, institutions that lack skilled personnel or fail to integrate MIS into daily operations may experience limited performance gains, despite having advanced technology in place.

While global tertiary institutions continue to improve performance through digital systems, the African higher education sector faces more serious challenges. Universities across Africa struggle with weak institutional capacity, inadequate ICT infrastructure, resistance to change and limited technical skills among academic and administrative staff (World Bank, 2019). These challenges affect the ability of MIS to function effectively and contribute to organisational performance. Studies indicate that although MIS adoption is increasing in African universities, practical use remains low, resulting in inefficiencies in record management, planning, and service delivery (UNESCO, 2021). This gap highlights the difference between the potential of MIS and its actual contribution to institutional performance.

Nigeria reflects this broader African challenge, despite increased investment in tertiary education, performance outcomes remain uneven across institutions. Government agencies such as the Tertiary Education Trust Fund (TETFund) have invested heavily in infrastructure, ICT development, staff training, and research support. Between 2011 and 2022, TETFund disbursed approximately ₦1.9 trillion to about 220 public tertiary institutions across Nigeria, funding physical infrastructure, ICT facilities, laboratories, libraries and providing scholarships and staff capacity-building opportunities (TETFund, 2024; Guardian Nigeria, 2024). However, reports indicate that many institutions still rely on manual or poorly integrated information systems, leading to inefficiencies, duplication of effort, and weak decision-making processes (National Universities Commission [NUC], 2022). Moreover, regional disparities in MIS adoption and use are evident within Nigeria. Studies comparing institutions across regions show that tertiary institutions in southern Nigeria perform better in the use of MIS than those in the northern regions, largely due to better ICT infrastructure, higher digital literacy, and stronger institutional support (Adebayo & Akinwale, 2020). In contrast, several institutions in northern Nigeria face challenges such as limited access to functional MIS platforms, inadequate training, and low practical utilization of existing systems, contributing to weaker organisational performance and slower administrative processes.

The problem is not only the availability of MIS but also the skills and practical competence required to use it effectively. Research shows that MIS improves organisational performance only when users possess adequate technical skills, receive continuous training, and are supported by management (O'Brien & Marakas, 2019). In many Nigerian tertiary institutions, it is observed that staff lack the practical skills needed to fully operate MIS tools, while others resist system use due to poor understanding or fear of technology. As a result, MIS systems are often underutilised, limiting their impact on performance (Ibrahim & Mustapha, 2021; Ojo & Akinyemi, 2018).

Despite growing studies on MIS and organisational performance, most literature focuses on system availability or adoption rather than how staff skills and practical usage affect actual performance outcomes (Ogbunude, Obi & Nwankwo, 2021; Lawal & Afolayan, 2023; Yamoah, Attafuaah & Nketia, 2024; Purnamasari & Hindria, 2025; Matimbwa & Kamala, 2024; Abid & Khan, 2024; Kurniawati & Raharja, 2024; Naser, Hidayati & Pardiman, 2025; Ogbunude, Obi & Nwankwo, 2024; Lawal & Afolayan, 2024). There is limited empirical evidence explaining why MIS investments have not consistently translated into measurable performance improvements, especially in northern Nigerian tertiary institutions. This highlights the need for further investigation into how MIS can be effectively leveraged to enhance organisational performance. Against this backdrop, this study examines how Management Information Systems influence organisational performance in selected state tertiary institutions in Sokoto State.

1.2 Research Questions

- i. What are the level of MIS application on organisational performance in selected tertiary institution in Sokoto State?
- ii. Does MIS utilisation influence organisational performance in selected state tertiary institutions in Sokoto State?

- i. To what extent does staff Competence in operating Management Information Systems influence organisational performance in selected state tertiary institutions in Sokoto State?

1.3 Research Hypotheses

- i. Management Information Systems application does not significantly influence organisational performance in selected state tertiary institutions in Sokoto State.
- ii. MIS utilisation does not significantly influence organisational performance in selected state tertiary institutions in Sokoto State.
- iii. Staff Competence in operating Management Information Systems does not significantly influence organisational performance in selected state tertiary institutions in Sokoto State.

Literature Review

Management Information System (MIS) are recognized as essential tools for improving organisational performance through the provision of accurate, timely and relevant information for effective decision-making and operational control. MIS is defined as an integrated system of people, technology and procedures through which information is collected, processed, stored and disseminated to support planning, coordination and institutional management (Laudon & Laudon, 2022). In tertiary institutions, administrative efficiency is enhanced through MIS by facilitating student records management, staff administration, financial monitoring and academic coordination. When reliable information is made available through MIS, informed decisions are enabled, resources are efficiently allocated and service delivery is improved. Organisational coordination is also strengthened and operational inefficiencies are reduced through MIS, resulting in improved overall performance (O'Brien & Marakas, 2019). Thus, MIS is regarded not only as a technological system but also as a strategic institutional resource that contributes to organisational effectiveness.

However, organisational performance improvement is largely determined by the level of MIS application within institutional process. MIS application is described as the extent to which information system are integrated into routine organisational activities such as planning, reporting, monitoring and control. Improved efficiency, better information management and stronger institutional control are achieved when MIS is properly applied in organisational operations (Stair & Reynolds, 2020). In tertiary institutions, transparency is enhanced, administrative delays are minimized and accountability is strengthened when MIS is effectively applied (UNESCO, 2021). Nevertheless, performance improvements cannot be achieved solely through the availability of MIS unless it is properly applied in daily institutional activities. Therefore, MIS application is considered an important link between system availability and actual organisational performance outcomes.

In addition, MIS utilization is identified as a critical factor influencing organisational performance. MIS utilisation refers to the extent and frequency with which staff and management use information systems in performing their responsibilities. Improved decision-making quality, better coordination and reduced operational errors are achieved when MIS is consistently utilized (Turban, Pollard & Wood, 2018). Faster responses to administrative demands and improved service delivery are also facilitated through effective MIS utilization. However, when MIS is underutilized, its potential benefits are not fully realized and organisational performance improvements are limited (World Bank, 2021). This indicates that organisational performance is influenced not only by system availability but also by the extent to which MIS is actively utilized in institutional operations.

Furthermore, the effectiveness of MIS application and utilization is largely influenced by staff competence. Staff competence is defined as the knowledge, technical skills and ability required for effective operation and use of MIS. Improved system effectiveness and better decision-making outcomes are achieved when MIS is operated by competent personnel (Laudon & Laudon, 2022). Efficient use of MIS, improved data accuracy and better institutional coordination are facilitated when staff possess adequate technical competence. Conversely, when staff lack the required competence, MIS may be underutilized, misapplied or avoided, thereby limiting its contribution to organisational performance (Ojo & Akinyemi, 2018). Therefore, staff competence is considered a critical enabling factor through which

the effectiveness of MIS application and utilization is strengthened, resulting in improved organisational performance

Empirical evidence has also shown that MIS utilization and staff competence significantly influence organisational performance across different institutional contexts. For example, it was found by Matimbwa and Kamala (2024) that system user competencies significantly influenced information quality and MIS performance in local government authorities in Tanzania, indicating that system effectiveness is largely determined by user capability. Similarly, improved operational efficiency, workflow coordination, and decision-making were reported by Abid and Khan (2024) as outcomes of strategic MIS utilization in private firms, although staff competence was not examined alongside utilization. In the same manner, a positive effect of MIS utilization on organisational performance was reported by Kurniawati and Raharja (2024), although their study was limited to a single enterprise and competence effects were not isolated. Furthermore, significant effects of user competence on performance were reported by Naser, Hidayati, and Pardiman (2025) in a university context, although systematic utilization patterns were not examined. Although the importance of MIS utilization and staff competence has been established, these variables have mostly been examined separately or outside tertiary institutional settings. Therefore, there remains a need for the combined influence of MIS application, utilization, and staff competence on organisational performance to be examined within the context of state tertiary institutions in Sokoto State, Nigeria.

Empirical studies further support the relationship between MIS, utilization, competence, and organisational performance. For instance, Matimbwa and Kamala (2024) found that system user competencies significantly influenced information quality and MIS performance in local government authorities in Tanzania, indicating that user skills determine system effectiveness and organisational outcomes. Similarly, Abid and Khan (2024) reported that strategic utilization of MIS improved operational efficiency, workflow coordination, and decision-making in private firms in Indonesia, although their study did not examine staff competence alongside utilization. In the same vein, Kurniawati and Raharja (2024) found that increased MIS utilization positively affected organisational performance through improved data management and employee engagement, but their study focused on a single enterprise and did not isolate competence effects. Furthermore, Naser, Hidayati, and Pardiman (2025) found that user competence significantly influenced performance in a university setting, although their study focused on lecturers and did not examine utilization patterns. While these studies confirm that MIS utilization and competence influence performance, most were conducted outside tertiary institutions or examined these variables separately. Therefore, there remains a need to examine how MIS application, utilization, and staff competence jointly influence organisational performance in tertiary institutions, particularly in state tertiary institutions in Sokoto State, Nigeria.

2.2 Theoretical Framework

This study uses the combination of both Resource-Based View (RBV) propounded by Barney in a year 1991 and Technology **Acceptance Model (TAM)** by Davis, 1989 as a theoretical framework that help to explain how MIS (Utilization and Competence) contributes to organisational performance. RBV focuses on how an organisation's **internal resources and capabilities** create a sustainable performance advantage (Barney, 1991), while TAM explains how **user perceptions and competence** influence the acceptance and effective use of technology (Davis, 1989). Combining these theories allows a clear understanding of both the **strategic value of MIS as an organisational resource** and the **human factors that determine its practical impact on performance**.

According to RBV, organisations achieve superior performance when they deploy resources that are **valuable, rare, inimitable, and non-substitutable** (Barney, 1991). In this context, **Management Information Systems (MIS)** are considered strategic resources whose value depends on **effective utilization and the competence of staff** in using system outputs for decision-making, planning, and coordination (Matimbwa & Kamala, 2024; Yamoah et al., 2024). Studies by Lawal and Afolayan (2024) and Ogbunude et al. (2021) show that the availability of MIS alone does not automatically improve performance; rather, performance gains occur when **staff actively use MIS functionalities** such as retrieving data, generating reports, and analyzing information.

Complementing RBV, TAM emphasizes that **perceived usefulness and ease of use** shape the intention to use technology, while user competence determines **actual utilization** (Davis, 1989; Venkatesh & Bala, 2008). Empirical studies indicate that staff with higher MIS competence are more likely to exploit system capabilities effectively, resulting in improved decision-making, operational efficiency, and service delivery (Matimbwa & Kamala, 2024; Yamoah et al., 2024). This explains why organisations with MIS in place may still underperform if staff lack the skills to apply system outputs in daily operations.

RBV view MIS as a strategic resource, the TAM explains how **staff competence and utilization behavior** determine whether MIS contributes meaningfully to organisational outcomes. This integration aligns with the study's research questions by linking **MIS application, utilization and staff competence** directly to **organisational performance**. From the above theories, the study provides the conceptual model to help visualized how Management Information Systems influence organisational performance in tertiary institution in Sokoto State. The model proposes that both high utilization and strong competence are needed for MIS to improve organisational performance, measured by operational efficiency, timely decision-making, quality of service, and staff productivity (Diis & Kiiru, 2024; Mwanza et al., 2023). In line with RBV, MIS represents a strategic organisational resource whose value is realized only when complemented by skilled personnel, and according to TAM, the perception and ability of users to engage with the system determine the actual use of these technological resources (Barney, 1991; Davis, 1989). Therefore, the model highlights that organisational performance is not solely determined by the presence of MIS tools but by the **combined effect of how well staff are skilled and how actively they utilize the system**. The conceptual model (Figure 1) below illustrates the connection between **MIS application, utilisation, staff competence, and organisational performance**, showing that performance improves only when staff effectively use and apply MIS resources.

Figure 1: Conceptual/Research Model

METHODOLOGY

This study is positivist and quantitative in nature. **Positivist research paradigm**, is adopted, because it emphasizes on objective measurement and empirical testing of relationships among observable variables (Creswell, 2014; Saunders, Lewis, & Thornhill, 2019). Consistent with this paradigm, a **quantitative research approach** was employed to examine the effects of **MIS application, utilisation and staff competence on organisational performance** among non-academic staff in selected state-owned tertiary institutions in Sokoto State.

The study population is 180 comprised only non-academic staff actively involved in using MIS or ICT in their daily activities in three selected tertiary institutions in Sokoto State. Specifically, **Sokoto State University (SSU) had (50) relevant staff, Umaru Ali Shinkafi Polytechnic, Sokoto, (70) staff across seven colleges, and Shehu Shagari College of Education (now University of Education) (60) staff.** Using Krejcie and Morgan's (1970) sample size determination table, a sample of 123 respondents was deemed appropriate for the population size, ensuring statistically valid results. A stratified random sampling technique was applied, with each institution and college representing a stratum, followed by

simple random sampling within each stratum to achieve proportional representation and minimize selection bias.

Primary data were collected through a structured questionnaire, administered online via Google Forms and physically through self-administered copies. The questionnaire was adapted from validated instruments in previous studies on MIS, staff competence, and organisational performance (Lawal & Afolayan, 2024; Matimbwa & Kamala, 2024; Yamoah et al., 2024; Ogbunude et al., 2021). A five-point Likert scale was used, ranging from 1 = Strongly Disagree to 5 = Strongly Agree. The questionnaire measured three main constructs: MIS application, utilisation (data retrieval, report generation, and information analysis); staff competence (technical skills, ability to interpret MIS outputs, and practical application in decision-making) and organisational performance (operational efficiency, timely decision-making, quality of service, and staff productivity).

Data analysis was conducted with the help of SPSS version 27 to ensure all the assumption of regression analysis were met and also use multiple regression analysis to test the study hypotheses.

Result, Findings and Discussion

Out of 123 questionnaires distributed both through Google form and self-administration, 114 were successfully retrieved and found valid. This represents a 92.6% response rate, which is considered very good and adequate for quantitative, survey research. This rate is in line with the recommendation of Babbie (2007) who stated that a response rate of 50% is considered adequate, 60% is good and 70% and above is very good. Therefore, this response rate will be used to conduct both descriptive and inferential analyses using SPSS version 27, as presented below

4.1 Descriptive Statistics of the Variable

This section presents the descriptive statistics of the latent variable employed in this study to summarize perception of respondents relating to the MIS application, utilisation, staff competency of MIS and organisational performance. The results are presented in the table below.

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics of MIS application, utilisation, Staff Competency and Organisational Performance

Variables	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
MISA	114	1.00	4.80	3.2146	1.10237
MISU	114	1.00	5.00	2.8454	1.18041
SC	114	1.60	4.60	2.8632	1.27851
OP	114	1.20	4.40	3.4874	.91075
Valid N (listwise)	114				

Source: SPSS Output, 2025

The Table 1 shows that MIS application has a mean score of 3.21 with a standard deviation of 1.10. Since the mean value is above the threshold of 3.00, this indicates that MIS tools and systems are present and are being applied to some extent in the selected tertiary institutions in Sokoto State. This suggests that MIS has been integrated into certain institutional functions such as record management, administrative coordination, and information processing. The relatively moderate standard deviation indicates that responses from staff were fairly consistent, implying that MIS application exists across the institutions, although the level of application may vary slightly among departments and units.

However, the MIS utilization (MISU) result shows that mean score of 2.85 with a standard deviation of 1.18. Since the mean value is below the threshold of 3.00, this indicates that most of the respondents in SSU, COE and UASP disagreed that MIS is adequately utilized in these institutions. This implies that MIS facilities and systems are not fully or effectively used from administrative and academic decision making. This is evident because the students still access some of the institutions service manually like hostel accommodation, result, notification and certificates and other important services. The high standard deviations suggest a differences un staff responses, meaning that while some staff members make use of MIS, many others experience limited usage, possibly due to unequal access, inadequate infrastructure or lack of institutional support.

In a similar view, staff competency (SC) concerning their skills in the use of MIS recorded a mean score of 2.86 with a standard deviation of 1.28. this mean is slightly below 3.00 threshold, indicating that respondents generally felt that, their competency in MIS used is not adequate. This suggest that many staff members lack sufficient skill, training or confidence in using MIS tools. The high standard deviation further shows that staff response varied, implying that some staff are competent in MIS usage, while a significant number are not, reflecting uneven capacity across the institution

In contrast, organisational performance (OP) recorded a mean score of **3.49** with a standard deviation of **0.91**, which is above the benchmark of 3.00. This indicates that respondents generally agreed that their institutions are performing well in terms of efficiency, effectiveness, and service delivery. The moderate level of variation in responses suggests that although most staff perceive improved performance, a few still experience performance challenges in certain areas.

Based on the response above, it reveals that, there is present of MIS in the selected tertiary institutions, but, utilization and staff competence are very low, this mean that the level of organisational performance may not be fully driven by effective MIS practice.

4.2 Multiple Regressions

This section present the result of multiple regression analysis conducted to test the study hypotheses.

Table 5: Coefficient Result of MIS (MIS application, utilization, Staff Competency) and Organisational Performance

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
1 (Constant)	.329	.195		1.692	.092
MISA	.118	.042	.121	2.810	.006
MISU	.013	.034	.016	.372	.710
SC	.076	.051	.049	7.141	.000

a. Dependent Variable: OP

Source: SPSS Output, (2025)

H_0^1 : MIS application does not significantly affect organisational performance in selected tertiary institutions in Sokoto State.

The coefficient result of the multiple regression shows that MIS application has a positive and statistically significant effect on organisational performance. This is evident from the regression values (B = .118, Beta = .121, Sig. (p) = .006). This indicates that an increase in the level of MIS application is associated with a corresponding increase in organisational performance. In practical terms, this means that when MIS is properly applied in institutional activities such as student records management, administrative coordination, financial monitoring, and reporting processes, organisational efficiency and service delivery are enhanced. The positive beta value further indicates that organisational performance is meaningfully influenced by MIS application, although the strength of the influence is moderate compared to staff competency. This finding suggests that improved access to accurate information, better decision-making, and stronger administrative control are facilitated when MIS is integrated into routine institutional processes, thereby improving institutional performance. This is also consistent with the descriptive findings, where a mean score above the benchmark value of 3.00 was recorded for MIS application, indicating that agreement was expressed by most staff that MIS is applied in various institutional functions. Therefore, it can be practically inferred that organisational performance improvement is significantly supported by the extent to which MIS is applied in institutional operations in the selected tertiary institutions. Furthermore, since the significance value of .006 is less than the p-value threshold of 0.050, the null hypothesis is rejected. This implies that a statistically significant influence on organisational performance is exerted by MIS application in the selected tertiary institutions in Sokoto State.

H₀² MIS utilisation does not significantly affect organisational performance in selected tertiary institutions in Sokoto State.

The coefficient result of the multiple regression shows that MIS utilisation has a positive but statistically insignificant effect/influence on the organisational performance. This is evident in the values (B = .013, Beta = .016, Sig (p) = .710). This indicates that while increases in MIS utilization are associated with slight improvements in organisational performance, the effect is not strong enough to be statistically meaningful. In other words, the low usage of MIS in administrative and academic processes across the institutions limits its capacity to significantly drive performance outcomes. This is consistent with the descriptive statistics, where MIS utilization had a mean score of 2.85, below the benchmark of 3.00, reflecting that most staff disagreed that MIS is adequately used. Therefore, we can say that practically, this revealed that although some staff occasionally make use of MIS tools for decision-making and service delivery, the current level of integration is insufficient to influence the overall performance of the institutions. Therefore, since the sig value 0.710 is below the p-value threshold which is 0.050, the null hypothesis is accepted, maintaining that MIS utilization, in its current state, is not a significant determinant of organisational performance in the selected tertiary institutions.

H₀³ Staff competency in MIS does not significantly affect organisational performance in selected tertiary institutions in Sokoto State.

The table 5 Coefficient result of multiple regressions result indicates that staff competency has a positive and statistically significant effect on organisational performance (B = 0.076, Beta = 0.049, Sig (p) = .001). This implies that increases in staff competency, such as better skills, knowledge, and confidence in using MIS tools, lead to measurable improvements in organisational performance. Staff with higher competency are able to navigate MIS systems more effectively, make accurate administrative decisions, and ensure that academic and service processes run efficiently. This finding aligns with the descriptive statistics, where staff competency had a mean score of 2.86, slightly below the benchmark, showing variation in skill levels. The regression result demonstrates that even a small improvement in staff skills can strongly influence performance, highlighting the critical role of human capacity in leveraging MIS systems to achieve better institutional outcomes. Therefore, since the sig value 0.001 is below the P-value 0.050 threshold, the null hypothesis two (H₀²) is **rejected**, confirming that staff competency significantly affects organisational performance in the selected tertiary institutions.

4.3.1 DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Based on the result of the analysis above on Management Information System and Organisational Performance in selected tertiary institution in Sokoto State. The study found that:

MIS Application and Organisational Performance in Selected Tertiary Institutions in Sokoto State

The findings of this study showed that MIS application has a positive and statistically significant influence on organisational performance in in the selected tertiary institutions in Sokoto State. This was confirmed by the regression result (B = .118, Beta = .121, Sig = .006), which indicated that organisational performance improves significantly when MIS properly applied in institutional process. Therefore, since the significance value (.006) is less than the acceptable threshold of 0.050, the null hypothesis was rejected and it was concluded that MIS application significantly influences organisational performance. This implies that the integration of MIS into institutional activities such as record management, administrative coordination, reporting, and financial monitoring enhances efficiency, improves decision-making, and strengthens service delivery. This finding is consistent with existing literature, which states that organizational effectiveness and performance are improved when MIS is properly integrated into routine operations (Laudon & Laudon, 2022; O'Brien & Marakas, 2019). It also supports the argument that the benefits of MIS are achieved not merely through system availability but through its effective application in organizational processes, which enhances transparency, monitoring, and administrative effectiveness (Stair & Reynolds, 2020; UNESCO, 2021). Therefore, it was concluded that MIS application serves as a key factor in improving organizational performance, and its proper integration into

institutional operations is essential for achieving improved efficiency and overall institutional effectiveness.

MIS Utilization and Organisational Performance of Selected Tertiary Institution in Sokoto State

The result of the analysis shows that MIS utilization has a positive but statistically insignificant influence on the performance of selected tertiary institutions in Sokoto State. This indicates that, increasing use of MIS tools has not significantly improved institutional performance because the tools were either not effectively utilized or are not sufficient in the study area. This underutilization of MIS limits the potential efficiency in timely decision making and stream lined administrative process that can be translate in to the overall performance and service delivery. This finding are in line with the study of Yamoah et al (2024) and Lawal & Afolayan (2023) who in their studies shows that organisational benefits are realized only when systems are actively used to retrieve data, generate reports and analyze information toward achieving the overall performance of the organisation. In addition to that, UNESCO (2021) and the study conducted by Ibrahim & Mustapha (2021) report that in many African institutions, low utilizations of MIS dues to inadequate infrastructure, limit access and weak institutional support results in minimal performance improvement. The Sokoto State tertiary institutions therefore, mirror these broader regional challenges, indicating that without proper integration and consistent use, MIS cannot be a major driver of organisational performance.

Staff Competency and Organisational Performance of Selected Tertiary Institution in Sokoto State

The result of the regression analysis also reveals that staff skills/competency in operating MIS has a positive and moderate significant influence on the performance of tertiary institutions in Sokoto State. This implies that the higher the staff skills, knowledge, and confidence in using MIS tools the higher performance of the institutions especially in decision-making, and service delivery. This is because a competent staff area able to interpret system outputs accurately, use MIS features for administrative tasks, and apply data-driven insights in managerial decision-making, which improves operational efficiency, record accuracy, and service quality. This findings is supported by the studies of conducted by Matimbwa & Kamala (2024), Naser et al. (2025), and Mensah & Boateng (2022), which highlight that user competence is critical in transforming MIS data into actionable decisions that positively affect organisational performance. Also the TAM theory by Davis (1989) support this result, as the theory give much emphasis on the usefulness and this actual system usage are always influence by the skills and confidence of staff.

Conclusion and Recommendations

The study concludes that the performance of the three selected state owned institutions in Sokoto State namely: Sokoto State University, Umaru Ali Shinkafi Polytechnic and Shehu Shagari College of Education Sokoto is not largely dependents on the mere adoption of MIS, but rather on the extent of its effective application, utilisation and the competency of staff. This is evidenced by the regression result, which showed that MIS application has a positive and statistically significant influence on organizational performance, indicating that when MIS is properly applied in institutional processes such as student record management, reporting, and administrative coordination, improvements in efficiency, service delivery, and decision-making are achieved. However, MIS utilisation was found to have an insignificant influence on the performance, as well as observations during the preliminary review, where many administrative and academic activities are still handled manually. For instance, students' results are still displayed on notice board instead of online portal, notification of results and certificates are collected manually, hostel accommodations area managed without digital systems and other process that could benefit from MIS integration remain largely paper-based. This indicates that although MIS exists and is applied in some areas, it is not fully or consistently utilized across institutional operations. In contrast, staff competency shows a significance results, playing very crucial role in enhancing the performance of these institutions as evidence from the result above, but, not all staff are sufficiently skilled in using MIS tools as the utilisation is uneven, which limits the full potential of the system to efficiently keep record and enhance service delivery. It is based on these that the study recommends that;

1. **The Tertiary institutions** (Sokoto State University, Umaru Ali Shinkafi Polytechnic and Shehu Shagari College of Education Sokoto) should ensure that MIS systems are fully integrated into daily academic and administrative activities, such as result management, hostel allocation, notifications, and certificate issuance. Encouraging consistent usage of MIS tools will reduce reliance on manual processes, minimize errors, and allow the institutions to fully benefit from technological solutions to enhance organisational performance.
2. **The Tertiary institutions** (Sokoto State University, Umaru Ali Shinkafi Polytechnic and Shehu Shagari College of Education Sokoto) should focus on improving the staff skills, knowledge and confidence in using MIS tools through targeted training, workshop and mentorship programme. Strengthening staff competency will ensure that existing MIS systems are effectively leveraged, leading to better administrative efficiency, improved decision-making, and enhanced overall organisational performance. In taking the staff for training, should be based on merit without showing any sign of favoritisms or bias.

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